

HIPERMAT

Advanced design, monitoring, development and validation of novel
High PERFORMANCE MATerials and components

Deliverable 1.2

Data Management Plan

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Prepared by	Fernando Santos	Company	Fundación AZTERLAN
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DISSEMINATION LEVEL

Dissemination Level (choose the suitable option)	
X	PU Public
	PP Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
	RE Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
	CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

DOCUMENT MODIFICATIONS CONTROL

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1 Introduction

This document represents the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the HIPERMAT project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 958196.

The DMP aims to ensure that the project data is soundly managed and follows the FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) whenever this is possible. Moreover, the DMP ensures that HIPERMAT activities are compliant with the H2020 Open Access policy which aims to improve and maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects.

The purpose of this Data Management Plan (DMP) is to provide an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy that will be used in the HIPERMAT project by the consortium with regard to the project research data. The DMP describes the data management life cycle for the research data to be collected, processed and/or generated. Furthermore, it describes what methodology and standards will be adopted, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open and how this data will be preserved during and after the project.

The DMP is not a fixed document, rather it is intended to be a living document in which information can be made available on a finer level of granularity through updates as the implementation of the project progresses and when significant changes occur. It is envisioned that the DMP will be reviewed in the steering committee meetings and new changes in identified datasets will be incorporated if modifications are approved. This DMP will include but won't be limited to new datasets, show changes in the already identified datasets, changes in consortium policies and plans or other potential external factors. AZTERLAN is responsible for the preparation of the DMP and gather all inputs from different partners to be presented in the steering committee. The DMP will have a specific point for analysis in the agenda in those meetings. The emission of new DMP revisions will depend on whether changes in its content will be incorporated or not.

2 Data Management description

The research data that will be generated during the HIPERMAT project can be divided within five classes:

- 1.- Background data declared by different partners in the CA or that because of requirements for performing the different project activities will be supplied by partners in the project from previous studies and that could be involved in the following 4 categories.
- 2.- Acquired observational data from industrial equipment (e.g. sensor data, environmental impact related data, production data).
- 3.- Experimental data from laboratory equipment and tests.
- 4.- Simulation data generated from modelling.
- 5.- Derived / processed data from previous categories

HIPERMAT is going to carry out mainly Research and Innovation activities and partners represented in the project are part of the value chain of the automotive sector manufacturing components. In this project are not envisioned partners as industrial competitors in the same market segment that could limit the data share among each other's. However, the criticality of the data and the rules that will assure the legal responsibility of its use is gathered in the Consortium Agreement (CA) of this project.

The consortium partners will strive to maximise openness and follow the FAIR principles whenever possible. It is expected from all consortium partners that if it is necessary, they will tend to apply data curation measures in order to hide the sensitive IPR information and prepare the derived datasets that could be opened. All HIPERMAT data that underlies scientific publications shall be made available via open-access online platforms, unless subject to protection.

2.1 Data identification and validation

All consortium partners are responsible to identify the appropriate data that should be managed within the DMP (either internal/restricted or open data). The data owners (i.e. project partners that have been involved in the data capture/generation and preparation) will provide information about the data introducing the data in the table represented by ANNEX 1: **Data management directory** The ANNEX will be sent to AZTERLAN to update the last edition with different partners demands and present it in the regular steering committee meetings inviting partners to identify new set of data to be opened and securely managed. The Steering Committee will discuss the type of data and its description and once agreed generate a new edition of the ANNEX that will be distributed to partners with new changes.

2.2 FAIR data

2.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

A specific folder will be dedicated in the ONEDRIVE storing unit of HIPERMAT for "data storage". The folder will incorporate ANNEX 1 for identification of each subfolder containing specific data type. Identification of each subfolder will be as follows:

[General data name] (HIPERMAT):

- [General data name]_HIPERMAT: short and unique data name

Each HIPERMAT dataset will get a unique name using the following convention:

[General data name] [Specific data name](HIPERMAT, v[ZZ]):

- [General data name]: short and unique data name
- [Specific data name]: Name specifying more the data linked with a trial, a date, a type of material....
- v[ZZ]: version of dataset.

With the general and specific data name the dataset could be referenced and identified through the project documentation and internal project storage platform. Moreover, the version of the data is a part of the data name in order to differentiate data versions.

Whenever the data will be made public, it will also get the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) which is a persistent and unique identifier. DOI is an alphanumeric string assigned to uniquely identify an object. It is tied to a metadata description of the object as well as to a digital location, such as a URL, where all the details about the object are accessible.

The DOI numbers will be provided either by the publisher when publishing data in an article (i.e. in a scientific journal) or by using the repositories that generate also DOI numbering. For this purpose, several different free services can be used, such as Zenodo <https://zenodo.org> or ResearchGate <https://www.researchgate.net> (see Table 1). Each specific version of data that will be declared as public will get only one DOI, which will serve as the main digital identifier of the data as well as to a digital location. This DOI should be consistently used in order to reference the data for reporting and dissemination purposes. If the data will not get a DOI (private/internal data), a unique dataset name should be used for referencing purposes, following the convention described above.

When uploading the data either on a public or an internal (i.e. owned by one of the HIPERMAT partners) repository, the data should be accompanied by information that will facilitate their understanding and re-use by interested stakeholders. The basic information that will assist interested stakeholders and a systematic overview of the data properties will be described using ANNEX 1. The form consists of a set of characteristics and serve as a template to collect and present basic details about data, including its format and file type as well as meaningful information about who created or contributed to the dataset, its name and reference, date of creation, under what conditions it may be accessed etc.

2.2.2 Making data openly accessible

In order to expand the impact of the HIPERMAT project, the consortium partners will maximise their effort to facilitate sharing of results and deliverables within and beyond the consortium. Selected data and results will be shared with the scientific community and other stakeholders through publications in scientific journals and presentations at conferences, as well as through open access data repositories.

All data owners should agree on data openness. If the data cannot be made open, the data owners will clearly justify why data cannot be made openly accessible. The main elements when considering confidentiality of datasets are:

- to protect intellectual property regarding underlying processes, products and technologies where the data could be used to derive sensitive information that would impact the competitive advantage of the consortium or its members;
- commercial agreements as part of the procurements of components or materials that might foresee the confidentiality of data.
- personal data that might have been collected in the project, where sharing them is not allowed by the national and European legislation.

The SC will also verify in the regular meetings if any of the DMP data could and should be made open. The SC may appeal and suggest the data owners to apply measures that will resolve the IPR issues that

barrier the data openness. A subset of data or modified data could be generated out of the original data in order to provide an open version of original data.

Generally, all research data underpinning publications should be made available for verification and re-use unless there are justified reasons for keeping specific datasets confidential. For data storage and backup different services can be used that offer open access. The list of the services that will be used within the HIPERMAT project are overviewed in Table 1. Specific data can be stored in more than one repository. Consortium partners will have a possibility to store their datasets in a repository governed by the project coordinator (i.e. ONEDRIVE service on private server at AZTERLAN).

Table 1 Overview of data hosting and listing options

Service provider	Type of service	Costs	Intended use	Retention period
AZTERLAN	ONEDRIVE server from AZTERLAN	Free of charge	Upload and backup of internal and open data, internal and public links, access restrictions	at least 3 years after the end of project
SPIRE https://www.aspire2050.eu/	HIPERMAT website hosted on private server at SPIRE website	Free of charge	Data, documents and information about the project	at least 3 years after the end of project lifespan
Zenodo https://zenodo.org	Open Science Services	Free of charge	Data hosting (up to 50GB), data listing, DOI generation	unlimited
ResearchGate https://www.researchgate.net	Add your research data	Free of charge	Data hosting (up to 512MB), data listing, DOI generation	unlimited
Elsevier. https://www.journals.elsevier.com/data-in-brief/	Data in Brief journal	\$600	Data paper submission, hosting, DOI generation	unlimited

Together with the data, supplementary material should be stored, that allows interpretation and use of the data (e.g. data summary, the associated metadata, documentation and code). If data accessibility problems or restrictions occur, the interested parties should directly expose the situation in the monthly meetings of the technical team or in the steering Committee meetings. The contact person represented by the project coordinator, is also in charge to grant additional data access permissions of the internal data or declare the individual conditions under which the data can be accessed.

2.2.3 Making data interoperable

To maximize the data interoperability (i.e. allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc.) the HIPERMAT data will be provided in standard formats that could as well be read by free and/or open software applications. That will simplify the data uptake and facilitate re-combinations with different datasets from different origins. Table 2 lists some of the standard formats and the accompanying free and/or open software applications that could be used. If

some other formats are used, the author of the data should also provide information of the appropriate software application that could be used to view or edit the data.

Table 2 Used formats and compatible open software application

Standard format	Free and/or open software application
PDF	Adobe Reader DC, WPS office
DOC, DOCX, XLS, XLSX, ODF, PPT, PPTX	OpenOffice, WPS office

Complementary data documentation should also be provided to encompass details on vocabularies and units of measurements. Wherever possible consortium partners will identify and use standard data and metadata vocabularies (e.g. IEC62264/ISA95 terminology, domain vocabulary) to maximise the data interoperability.

2.2.4 Making data re-useable

The identification of the location of the set of data, their utility and a coherent accessibility to other communities will allow to be used to build up new data bases, modelling tools and serve as the basis to continue with the development of materials, technical solutions and software. The permitted re-use of the HIPERMAT open data will be defined by the choice of the appropriate user license.

2.3 Allocation of resources

Costs related to open-access to research data in Horizon 2020 are eligible for reimbursement under the conditions defined in the H2020 Grant Agreement, in particular Article 6 and Article 6.2.D.3, but also other articles relevant for the cost category chosen. Costs cannot be claimed retrospectively. Project beneficiaries will be responsible for applying for reimbursement of costs related to making data accessible to others beyond the consortium.

2.4 Data security

HIPERMAT will use methods that emphasize easy access and trust among the participants. The following guidelines will be followed to ensure the security of the data:

- Store data in at least two separate locations to avoid loss of data (e.g. HIPERMAT repository and local storage at data owner's location for backup).
- Storage data owner (AZTERLAN) has a specific routine of security copies each week to allow to recover data in most recent version.
- Label files and versions in a systematically structured way to ensure coherence of the final data.

2.5 Ethical aspects

Currently, no additional ethical or legal issues have been identified, other than the ones discussed in D8.1. Consortium members may arise any aspect linked specifically with activities to be performed over the umbrella of this project, that may be conditioned by international, state, regional or internal company regulations or legal conflicts affecting ethics including but not limited to social, health or safety aspects.

In deliverable D8.1 the applicant must demonstrate that appropriate health and safety procedures conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation are followed for staff involved in this project, also copies of authorisations for relevant facilities will be gathered.

Data as specific requirements for external access to facilities and work performance linked with HIPERMAT project won't be commonly shared but will be of access on demand for those partners that will develop activities on facilities of other partners.

3 Overall Data Management Plans

Different data have been identified based on background included in CA by partners and as outputs linked with activities described in different WPs. Data will be identified by different fields in ANNEX 1 described as the data management plan directory. This document will be reviewed at least in each steering committee meeting and if needed will be updated and shared between partners to assure FAIR use of data.

Definition of datasets will include:

- **General definition of datasets** including: Data number, data name, data type, data description, date of creation, format of data.
- **Datasets generation** : Data origin, contributors and roles.
- **Archiving and preservation**: Location, DOI, retention period.
- **Data exploitation and sharing**: Data openly available (y/n), Level of accessibility, data utility.

4 Conclusion

This Data Management Plan is separated in two differentiated documents for efficient data management performance:

- The data management plan that will incorporate all the definitions and data management procedures for data FAIR management.
- The directory of datasets in ANNEX 1 for a quick follow up and update of datasets in terms of their definition, generation, archiving, preservation exploitation and sharing.

The data management plan will be reviewed in each steering committee meeting whereas ANNEX 1 is a more dynamic document that can be reviewed as far as new data sets arise and the coordinator can decide over including them and share the document for data protection prior to the steering committee meeting.

References

- [1] EUROPEAN COMMISSION, H2020 Programme, Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020, Version 3.0, 26 July 2016, https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf.
- [2] EUROPEAN COMMISSION, H2020 Programme, Open access & Data management – H2020 Online Manual, https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-dissemination_en.htm.
- [3] Zenodo, <https://zenodo.org/>.
- [4] Researchgate, <https://www.researchgate.net/>.
- [5] Elsevier, Data in Brief journal, <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/data-in-brief/>.
- [6] SPIRE. <https://www.spire2030.eu>

Format ANNEX 1. Directory of data sets HIPERMAT

Data number	Data name	Data type	Data description			Date of creation	Format of data
1	High entropy alloys mechanical properties performance	Patent and experimental data of alloy properties	Data obtained from trials in the development of the high entropy alloys, including chemical compositions, mechanical properties and microstructures obtained during their validation			2021-2022	.docx
	Data origin	Contributors	Roles	Location	DOI	Retention period	
	Internal development	AZTERLAN/CEIT	Development of chemical composition and validation of alloys	Share point/folder high entropy alloys. Mechanical properties. HIPERMAT.v1		Duration of the project	
	Data openly available (Y/N)	Level of accesibility		Data utility			
	No/Yes	Open once data susceptible for patenting the application proces have been protected		LMD companies involved in protective layers application			
Data number	Data name	Data type	Data description			Date of creation	Format of data

2	High creep resistant alloys/ chemical composition/mechanical properties	Chemical composition and experimental data of mechanical tests	Data obtained linked with chemical composition variations of stainless steels and their mechanical properties in terms of creep, hardness, wear resistance, crack propagation rate, thermal fatigue and microstructure.			2021-2022	.docx, .xlsx
	Data origin	Contributors	Roles	Location	DOI	Retention period	
	Test carried out during the project activities performance.	AZTERLAN/KTH/SVUM/QUESTEK	Material modelling and chemical composition selection	Sharepoint folder: High creep resistant alloys. Chemical composition. HIPERMAT.v1		Duration of the project	
	Data openly available (Y/N)	Level of accesibility		Data utility			
	N/Y	Open once data susceptible for patenting any new alloy have been protected		Data can be used for energy processing companies by using advanced materials for their construction.			
Data number	Data name	Data type	Data description			Date of creation	Format of data
3	Hydrosolidification /thermal data	Data from equipment design and process configuration	Data linked with machine details, machine performance in terms of fluid flows, and cooling temperature of metal inside the mold			2021-2022	.docx, .xlsx
	Data origin	Contributors	Roles	Location	DOI	Retention period	

	Cooperation with foreign organization for technology development	AZTERLAN	Machine construction, molds manufacturing and control data storage	Sharepoint folder: Hydrosolidification.thermal data.HIPERMAT.v1		Duration of the project
	Data openly available (Y/N)	Level of accesibility		Data utility		
	N	Only for the simulation development. Calcom/ESI		Data can be used for the manufacturing of new components in the steel casting industry with advanced properties in terms of fatigue and creep.		
Data number	Data name	Data type	Data description		Date of creation	Format of data
4	Furnace constructive data	Data for furnace performance theoretical modelling	Technical drawings of the whole furnace with parameters of gas flow and data of the material characteristics that conform the different furnace components.		2021-2022	.docx, .xlsx
	Data origin	Contributors	Roles	Location	DOI	Retention period
	Data generated by GHI for furnace construction and resulting from modelling within the project	GHI	Theoretical modelling of furnace performance in terms of temperatures	Sharepoint folder: Furnace data.materials componentsw and thermal performance HIPERMAT.v1		Duration of the project

	Data openly available (Y/N)	Level of accesibility	Data utility
	N	After NDA signature between GHI, Fraunhofer and CRM.	Data can be used for the understanding the basic performance of the furnace and the data

More details about the expected content of the form are given above:

- *Data name* – Short and unique name of the data following the convention described in 2.2.1.
- *Data type* – The type of study in the frame of which the dataset is produced.
- *DOI (if available)* – If the dataset is public DOI number must be provided (for details see 2.2.1).
- *Date of creation* – Date of creation of the dataset.
- *Contact person* – Contact details of the person in charge of the dataset responsible to provide additional information and support about the data.
- *Data description, purpose and relation to the project objectives* – A concise description of the data together with references to the HIPERMAT objectives, WPs and Tasks.
- *Data origin* – From where the data was captured/generated?
- *Contributors and roles* – List of project partners that were involved in data capture and preparation and their roles.
- *Data utility* – Potential external stakeholders for whom the data may prove useful (to whom it might be useful).
- *Format of data* – The format and volume of the dataset.
- *Location* – Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited (storage and backup)?
- *Retention period* – Length of time for which the data will remain re-usable
- *Data openly available (y/n)* – Will the data be openly available?
- *Level of accessibility* – If data is not openly available define who and under what conditions can access and use the data (provisions regarding the confidentiality of the data).

